

Tutorial: Using the TChecker VM

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1 Introduction

This tutorial provides a step-by-step guide for using the VM created with the GitHub Action `tchecker/vm.yml`. The VM includes the `tchecker` tool and the `tchecker-webapp`, along with example files. The default username and password for the VM are both `tchecker`.

2 Prerequisites

- VirtualBox installed on your system.
- The `tchecker.ova` file.

3 Importing the VM into VirtualBox

3.1 Using the VirtualBox GUI

1. Open VirtualBox.
2. Go to **File** → **Import Appliance**.
3. Follow the prompts to import the VM.
4. Start the VM and log in using the username and password `tchecker`.

3.2 Using the Command Line

1. Open a terminal or command prompt.
2. Navigate to the VirtualBox installation directory:

```
1 cd virtualbox-install-dir
```

3. Import the VM using the following command:

```
1 .\VBoxManage.exe import path/to/tchecker.ova --vsys 0 --  
vmname name-of-vm --unit 12
```

4. Start the VM from the VirtualBox GUI or using the command line.

4 Accessing the Examples

Some pre-compiled examples can be found at `/home/tchecker/Desktop/evaluation_models`.

All examples are located in the directory `/home/tchecker/tchecker_code/examples`. Each example consists of a shell script and a `.txt` file. The shell script generates a `.tck` file, which is used as input for `tchecker`.

1. Open a terminal in the VM.
2. Navigate to the examples directory:

```
1 cd /home/tchecker/tchecker_code/examples
```

3. Run the shell script for the desired example:

```
1 ./example_script.sh >> target.tck
```

4. Use `tchecker` to analyze the generated `.tck` file
5. For most tools, the description can be found at (<https://github.com/ticktac-project/tchecker/wiki/Using-TChecker>).
6. For comparison, the tool `tck-compare` is used:

```
1 tck-compare -h
```

5 Using the TChecker WebApp

5.1 Starting the WebApp

1. Open a terminal in the VM.
2. Navigate to the `tchecker-webapp` directory:

```
1 cd /home/tchecker/Desktop/webapp
```

3. Start the web application:

```
1 source venv/bin/activate
2 ./start.sh
```

4. Open a web browser and navigate to `http://localhost:5173`.

5.2 Analyzing Examples with the WebApp

1. Follow the steps in Section 4 to generate a `.tck` file.
2. Upload the `.tck` file to the web application.
3. Use the web interface to analyze the model.